

Certain philosophical preparations of food and beverage for sea-men, in their long voyages (1607)

by Hugh Platt

This 1607 advertisement was published in Kenneth Carpenter's book 'The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C'. It described the use of lemons and oranges for preventing scurvy.

The scanned original advertisement is available at:

<https://archive.org/details/b30338943>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/jywvse6h/items>

<https://www.proquest.com/eebo/docview/2240914936/44920395?sourcetype=Books>

https://famineanddearth.exeter.ac.uk/displayhtml.html?id=fp_00148_en_certainephilosophicalpreparations

Certaine philosophical preparations of foode and beverage for sea-men, in their long voyages: with some necessary, approved, and hermeticallyl medicines and antidotes, fit to be had in readinesse at sea, for prevention or cure of divers diseases.

Biographies and books

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hugh_Platt

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316091722.008>

https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_National_Biography,_1885-1900/Platt,_Hugh

<https://www.sal.org.uk/collections/explore-our-collections/collections-highlights/broadside-sir-hugh-platts-inventions/>

<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315608006-6/secrets-sir-hugh-platt-ayesha-mukherjee>

<https://archive.org/details/jevvelhouseofart00plat/page/n5/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30339972/page/n13/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/b30333404_0001/page/n7/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/delightsforladie00plat/page/n7/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b3033875x/page/n9/mode/2up>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

This text is available at:

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

Platt's advertisement on treatments of scurvy was cited in:

Keevil suggested that the juice that Lancaster had brought from London had been preserved by the secret process referred to by Sir Hugh Platt in the broadsheet (advertisement) that he issued in 1607. The document is of great interest, and the relevant portions are reprinted in the Appendix to this chapter [p.27-28]. He claimed that by using 'philosophical fire' (the scientific application of heat), he could preserve any kind of liquid from fermentation or other deterioration. It would seem that he was using the principles of sterile 'bottling' or 'canning,' the discovery of which is usually attributed to Nicholas Appert 200 years later. However, another writer has suggested recently that the 'fire' was simply a nostrum in the form of a powder which he added. In any case, Platt did not claim to have prepared the lemon juice for Lancaster, only that 'the juice of lemons was found [by him] to be an assured remedy for the scurvy.' His claim was that such juice, by 'fortifying it with his own fire, it will be lasting and durable,' whereas if not so treated, it would 'lose much of its first manifest nature, which it had while it was contained within its own pulp and fruit.' Platt ended his sheet with the warning that, if there was no speedy acceptance of his offer, he would give up devoting himself to the public good and turn to more profitable pursuits. This seems to have been what happened, as nothing more is heard of such preservation of foods and beverages. [p.18]

Carpenter KJ (1986) *The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*. 1986.

<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

In 1591–1594 James Lancaster (fl.1591–1618) made the first of many long sea voyages to Brazil and the East Indies. It was only on the third voyage of 1601–1603 that his flagship *Red Dragon* carried lemon juice, recommended by Sir Hugh Platt, presumably aware of Hawkins success with this treatment. [p.316]

Lancaster regarded his lemon juice a success and persuaded the East India Company to issue this juice on the voyages of 1604 and 1607, but this did not happen consistently. There was a special order for it in 1627, but on the juiceless 1678 voyage, half the ship's crew were disabled by scurvy and then cured by fresh limes and oranges. Platt also interpreted the result of Lancaster's use of his lemon juice as 'an assured remedy in the scurvy'. Platt was one of the first to address the problem of the loss of efficacy of citrus juices with time, and recommended 'the help of a sweet olive oil supernatant ... lest it lost much of his first manifest nature, which it has whilst it was contained within its own pulp and fruit'. [p.316]

Lind, in further editions of his book, maintained his belief in the efficacy of what was named in his 3rd edition as *rob*, until in the 1778 edition of his *Health of Seamen* he reformulated his syrup of lemons. Sound lemons are squeezed, the juice is filtered (but not boiled), put into small bottles no bigger than a pint, and olive oil poured into the neck of the bottle that is then corked and sealed – the precise system devised by Platt in 1607. [p.320]

Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment. *Nutr Rev.* 2009;67:315-32.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19519673>

Carpenter's Appendix, p.27-28, is on the following page.

Carpenter's note on p.27:

"An advertisement believed to have been published by Sir Hugh Platt in London in 1607, with some omissions and modernization of spelling."

Certain philosophical preparations of food and beverage for sea-men, in their long voyages

Hugh Platt

And first for Food. A cheap, fresh and lasting victual, called by the names of Macaroni amongst the Italians, and not unlike (save only in format) to the cuscus [couscous] in Barbary, may be upon reasonable warning provided in any sufficient quantity, to serve either for change and variety of meat, or in the want of fresh victual. With this, the Author furnished Sir Francis Drake and Sir John Hawkins, in their last voyage.

2. Any broth or colase [sieved extract], that will stand clear and liquid, and not jelly or grow thick when it is cold, may also be preserved by this fire of Nature from all mouldiness, sourness, or corruption, to any reasonable period of time that shall be desired. A necessary secret for all sick and weak persons at sea, when no fresh meat can be had, to strengthen or comfort them.

3. Now for Beverages: All the water, which to the purpose shall be thought needful to be carried to sea, will be warranted to last sweet, good, and without any intention to putrefaction, for 2, 3, or 4 years together. This is performed by a philosophical fire, being of a sympathetic nature with all plants and animals. In the space of one month, the Author will prepare so many tunnes [casks] thereof, as shall be reasonably required at his hands.

4. By this means also both Wine, Perry, Cider, Beer, Ale and Vinegar may be safely kept at sea, for any long voyage, without fear of growing dead, sour or musty.

5. And, as for Medicine, if any Nobleman, Gentleman, or Merchant shall by his physician be advised to carry any special distilled waters, decoctions or juices of any plant or any other liquid vegetable or animal body whatsoever with him in any long voyage, this Author will so prepare the same only by fortifying it with his own fire of kind, that he may be assured of the lasting and durability thereof, even at his own pleasure.

6. Here I may not omit the preparation of the juice of Lemons with this fire: Because it hath of late been found by that worthy Knight Sir James Lancaster to be an assured remedy in the scurvy, And though their juice will, by natural working and fermenting, in the end so spiritualize itself, as that it will keep and last either simply of it self, or by the help of a sweet olive oil supernatant: yet this Author is not ignorant, that it hath lost much of his first manifest nature, which it has whilst it was contained within its own pulp and fruit: (as is evident in the like example of wine, after it hath wrought long, which differeth exceedingly both in taste and nature from the grape out of which it is expressed) whereas being strengthened with this philosophical fire, it retaineth still both the natural taste, race [distinctive flavor], and verdure [freshness], that it had in the first expression: and so likewise of the Orange.

[Paragraphs 7-12 which deal with various medicines, have been omitted]

Thus much I am bold to offer and publish for the benefit of seafaring men, who for the most part are destitute both of learned Physicians and skillful Apothecaries: and therefore have more need than others to carry their own defensatives [prophylactics] and medicines about them. Which if it shall receive entertainment according to the worth thereof and my just expectation, I may happily be encouraged to pry a little further into Natures Cabinet, and so to disperse some of her most secret jewels, which she hath long time so carefully kept, only for the use of her dearest children: otherwise, finding no speedy or good acceptance of this my proffer (but rather crossed by malice or incredulity) I do here free and enlarge my self from mine own fetters: purposing to content my spirits, with such private and pleasing practices, as may better sort with my place and dignity, and in likelihood prove also more profitable in the end, than if I had thanklessly devoted my self to Bonum Publicum [the public good]. In which course, happy men are sometimes rewarded with good words: but few or none, in these days, with any real recompense.

H. P.